

PATIENTS' AWARENESS AND THE ISSUE OF MALARIA CHEMOPROPHYLAXIS

Anyanwu, E. B¹., Mabiku, T. O. ¹, and Okperi, B. ²

¹Department of Family Medicine, Faculty of Clinical Medicine, College of Health Science, Delta State University, Abraka, ²Department of Paediatrics, Faculty of Clinical Medicine, College of Health Science, Delta State University,

ABSTRACT

Malaria causes an acute febrile illness which maybe characterized by periods of febrile paroxysm. Mankind is infested by four species of the genus plasmodium, but *Plasmodium falciparum* predominates in the Sub-Saharan Africa. There is therefore a risk of non-immune travellers to malaria-endemic countries acquiring malaria. Exposure prophylaxis and chemoprophylaxis are established methods of preventing malaria during travel in malarial-endemic countries. Persons from non-endemic countries are considered non-immune and stand a chance of acquiring malaria with possible fatal outcome. This case report emphasizes the need for chemoprophylaxis for all returnees from non-endemic areas.

KEYWORDS: Patient awareness, counseling, chemoprophylaxis, diaspora

INTRODUCTION

Malaria infection is an endemic illness in the Sub-Saharan Africa in which Nigeria is located. Malaria infection has been reported to be responsible for the death of over one million people each year. These deaths are mainly in children under five years. Malaria infection of children during the first five years of life can cause severe and potentially fatal illness, which usually is rapidly progressive particularly in highly endemic region (WHO).

The risk of severe and potentially fatal infection is greater in person with little or no acquired immunity such as young children or immigrants from malaria free zones (Bremam 1988).

Severe malaria is usually confined to the first five years of life and becomes progressive less common with increasing age. Passive transfer of antibody across the placenta helps protect the neonate for the first six months of life, until he starts to acquire his own antibody by the age of six months. Following this period of relative protection, children become increasingly susceptible to the more severe clinical manifestation of malaria. But from around the fourth year of life, the severity of clinical attacks begins to decline. Deaths from malaria is uncommon after the fifth year of life and thereafter clinical attacks becomes less frequent and less severe until in adulthood when significant disease is uncommon (White and Strickland 1991).

Repeated malaria infection leads to the acquisition of a specific partial immunity by members of the indigenous population.

Our index case has lived all her life in a western country and never had malaria fever. Also she was aged only eighteen months and therefore her immunity against malaria was expectedly low or none at all.

Non-immune persons and other high risk people such as pregnant women, infants and young children should therefore be protected if they have to be in malaria zones and the aim of this study is to re-emphasize the need for chemoprophylaxis for such groups of persons and all non-immune travellers going to malaria zones.

CASE HISTORY

A young girl aged about 1½ years was brought into a busy group medicine practice by her mother and aunty with a history of a high grade fever for two days. Apparently, she has been managed at home with analgesics/antipyretic mixture and tepid sponging to no avail. There was an associated non-pruritic rash on her face and upper anterior chest wall. Appetite was poor, but she was not vomiting nor stooling.

Further questioning revealed that the family had just come back from their residence abroad and the young girl had never traveled outside the western country where they reside. Her parents have lived in that country for three uninterrupted years and this was the first girl's trip to Nigeria.

Apparently, the girl and even her parents were not placed on any kind of prophylaxis against malaria before they left the American continent where they live, and only started taking proguanil tablets on arrival here in Nigeria. She soon broke down with a high grade fever and a temperature maximum of 39.3^oc and was subsequently brought to the clinic.

Examination revealed a febrile child, who was not pale, not dehydrated and not cyanosed. Systemic examination was essentially normal.

A working diagnosis of malaria fever was made and a malaria parasite smear that was ordered for came back as positive (2⁺). She was subsequently started on an appropriate anti-malaria medication and an injectable antipyretic was administered to help lower the temperature.

She was reported to have been febrile overnight and her attendants spent the night tepid sponging her.

By the following morning, one of the baby's attendants who happened to be a trained health worker (based and work in Europe), came with the entourage that brought the baby girl back to the clinic. She "wondered aloud" why we did not "properly" educate them on what to expect following our line of management.

They claimed that all we told them was that the baby will be "alright", but that we did not explain to them what drugs we gave and what the drugs were expected to do. They also wondered why the baby still had a high temperature despite the medication that we gave to her.

She was essentially accusing us of not giving them a proper health talk which explains our diagnosis, the laboratory finding and then our line of management and choice of anti-malaria medication, and of any adverse reactions if any. They felt that we ought to have explained the therapeutic effect of all drugs given and our reason for choosing the medicines that we gave.

At this point, we had a group talk explaining the rationale for the choice of medication, what to expect and possible outcome. We also explained to them the expected rate of decline of temperature as we then encouraged them to give the medication as prescribed.

Finally, we again re-emphasized the need for a proper prophylaxis against malaria whenever they are to come home to Africa again.

DISCUSSION

Malaria infection is found commonly in the Sub-Saharan Africa in which Nigeria is found. It is responsible for about one million deaths each year, mainly in children under five years in Africa. An average child has about six bouts of malaria a year. Over a third of the world population live in zones where there is a high risk of infection (Chinnock, 1997).

Malaria is the most important parasitic disease of man. This human disease is a protozoan infection of red blood cells transmitted by the bite of a blood-feeding female *Anopheles* mosquito (White, 1996).

Malaria transmission occurs in more than 100 countries throughout Africa, Asia and Latin America. More than one billion inhabitants of these areas are exposed to risk of malaria infection. The estimated annual global incidence of malaria subsequently is over 200 million cases (White 1996, & Strickland 1991).

Malaria infection in children during the first five years of life can cause severe and potentially fatal illness, which usually is rapidly progressive particularly in highly endemic regions (WHO 1986).

The causative agent of this parasitic disease is Plasmodium. This protozoan is transmitted to man by the bite of the female Anopheles mosquito (Bouree, *et al* 1993).

Mankind is infected by four species of the genus plasmodium. These are *plasmodium falciparum*, *Plasmodium ovale*, *Plasmodium vivax* and *Plasmodium malariae*.

Only *Plasmodium falciparum*, the most widespread can lead to death through cerebral involvement in the form of cerebral malaria (Russel, 1995, Philips, 1990). *Plasmodium falciparum* predominates in the Sub-Sharan Africa, Papua New Guinea and Haiti.

Plasmodium falciparum is associated with the heaviest degree of parasitemia, and the severity of malaria that it causes is accentuated by the increasing resistance to commonly used drugs, requiring the use of more and more potent prophylactic and therapeutic agents (Gilbert, *et al.*, 2003 & Prince ., 1994).

Control measures are directed at reducing the population of anopheles mosquito, chemotherapy for infected persons and chemoprophylaxis for person traveling to endemic areas. The most important is the prevention of mosquito bites through the use of bed nets impregnated with insecticide, mosquito repellants and protective clothing (Warrel, 1993)

Infection by any of the human malaria species produces symptoms which, in non-immune subjects are temporarily debilitating and, in the case of *Plasmodium falciparum* are potentially fatal. Malaria should therefore be prevented if possible.

Those at most risk of contracting debilitating or life threatening malaria are:

- Children with sickle cell disease
- Pregnant mothers in endemic areas
- Child or adult who returns to an endemic area after an absence of over one year even if he/she is originally from that region.
- Non-immune individuals: people from non-endemic areas such as military personnel and other task forces working in malarious area.
- Indigenous populations in malarious areas before they have acquire protective immunity (i.e. infants and children up to the age of about five years) (Warrel, 1993 & Molyneux., 2002).

The state of immunity has a bearing on the use of drugs since people who have, by a prolonged exposure to the infection, acquired a degree of immunity can be cured or protected much more easily than those who have not.

The clinical manifestation of malaria is dependent on the previous status of the host. In areas of stable endemicity which includes Nigeria, repeated malaria infection leads to the acquisition of a specific partial immunity by members of the indigenous population. In these areas, people are infected repeatedly throughout their lives. Thus, a form of immunity develops which is sufficient to control, but not prevents infection (Marsh., 1993).

The risk of severe and potentially fatal infection is greater in persons with little or no acquired immunity such as young children or immigrants from malaria free areas (Bremam, *et al* 1988 & Warrel *et al.*, 1990).

All travelers to malarious area of the world are advised to use an appropriate drug regimen and personal protection measures to prevent malaria. However, travelers are to be informed that regardless of methods employed, malaria

may be contracted. Malaria symptoms can develop as early as eight days after initial exposure in a malaria-endemic area and as late as several months after departure from a malarious area, after chemoprophylaxis has been stopped. Travelers should understand that malaria can be treated effectively early in the course of the disease, but that delay of appropriate therapy can result in a serious or even fatal outcome (CDC, 1990 & CDC, 1993).

Because of the nocturnal feeding habits of Anopheles mosquitoes, malaria transmission occurs primarily at night. Travellers should take protective measures to reduce contact with mosquitoes especially during these times. Such measures include remaining in well-screened areas, using mosquito nets, and wearing clothes that cover most of the body.

Malaria chemoprophylaxis should begin 1 -2 weeks before travel to malarious area. This allows for any potential side effects to be evaluated and treated by the travellers' doctor before departure, and also assures for adequate blood levels of the drug before departure. Chemoprophylaxis should continue during travel in the malaria area and for 4 weeks after persons leaves the malarious areas (CDC, 1990 & CDC, 1993).

Children of any age can contract malaria; young children should avoid travel to areas with chloroquine-resistant *Plasmodium falciparum*, unless they can take a highly effective drug.

In a study to determine the effect of chemoprophylaxis on the case fatality rate of malaria, it was demonstrated that chemoprophylaxis significantly reduces fatality rates among non-immune malaria patients. This supports all efforts towards chemoprophylaxis (Kruase, *et al* 2006). Our index client was not given any chemoprophylaxis before she left the foreign country where she was delivered in and had lived her life before now.

She apparently contracted malaria while here in the country and promptly reported for proper evaluation. She did well eventually on management but then the risk taken could have been better avoided if proper prophylactic measures had been taken.

This report is essentially to call to our remembrance the need for prophylaxis wherever our kinsmen/women in diaspora are coming home for holidays or for any other ceremonies.

REFEREES

Bouree, P., Taugourdeau Ph., Ng – Anh Van. Malaria. In: Bouree, P., Taugourdeau, Ph. (Eds). Malaria, Smithkline Beecham Pharmaceuticals Bibliography; 1993 pp. 1 – 40.

Breman, J. G. and Campbell, C. C. Combating severe malaria in African children. *Bull WHO*, 1988; 66(5): 611 620.

Center for Disease Control and Prevention Recommendations for the Prevention of Malaria Among Travelers. March 09, 1990/39 (RR – 3); 1 – 10.

Center for Disease Control and Prevention Malaria: Health Information for International Travel <http://wonder.CDC.gov/wonder/prevguid/p0000375/p0000375.asp>.

Chinnock, P. Malaria: Action at last? *African Health*, 1997 September; Vol. 19, No. 6: pp 26 – 27.

Gilbert, D. N., Moellering, R. C., and Sande, M. A. Treatment of Parasitic Infections. In: The Sanford Guide to Anti-microbial Therapy. 33rd edition; 2003. Jeb. C. Sanford (Publisher) USA, pp. 90 – 97.

Kruase, G., Schoneberg, I., Altmann, D., and Stark, K. Chemoprophylaxis and malaria death rates. *Emerg infect Dis* (serial on the internet). 2006. <http://www.CDC.gov/ncidou/E1D/vol12no03/05-0736.htm>.

Marsh, K. Immunology of human malaria. In Gilles, H. M and Warrel, D. A. (Eds). Bruce – Chewatt's Essential Malariology. 3rd edition. Edward Arnold (Publ). 1993. pp. 60 – 78.

Molyneux, E. Malaria. In: Southall, D., Coulter, B., Ronald, C., Nicholson, S., and Parke, S (Eds). International Child Health Care: A Practical Manual for Hospitals Worldwide, Child Advocacy International. BMJ Books, 2002, pp. 473 – 476.

Philips, R. E., and Solomon, T. Cerebral malaria in Children. *The Lancet* 1990; 336: 1355 – 1360.

Prince, A. Infectious disease systemic protozoal infection-Malaria. In: Behraman, R. E., and Kliegman, R. M. (Eds). Nelson's Essential Pediatrics. 2nd edition. Philadelphia: WB Saunders Company; 1994, pp. 389 – 390.

Russel, W., Streel and Baffoe – Bonnie B. Cerebral Malaria in Children. *Pediatr Infect Dis. J.* 1995; 14 (4) 281 – 285.

Strickland, G. T. Infections of the blood and reticuloendothelial system-Malaria. In: Strickland, G.T (Ed). Hunters Tropical Medicine. 7th edition. Philadelphia; WB Saunders Company: 1991 pp 586 – 614.

Warrel, D. A. Treatment and Prevention of Malaria. In: Gilles, H. M., and Warrel, D. A (Eds). Bruce Chwatts Essential Malarialogy. 3rd edition. Edward Annold (Publ) 1993; pp. 163 – 195.

Warrel, D. A., Molyneux, M. E. and Beales, P. F. (Eds) World Health Organisation Division of Control of Tropical Disease. Severe and complicated malaria. 2nd edition. *Trans Roy Soc Trop Med Hyg*, 1990; 84 (Supplement 2) 1 – 65.

White, N. J. Malaria. In: Gordon C. Cook(Ed); Manson's Tropical Diseases. 20th edition. London; WB. Saunders Company; 1996. pp 1087 – 1164.

WHO Expert Committee on Malaria. Technical Report Series 18th Report, 735, 1986

Received for Publication: 02/04/2010

Accepted for Publication: 12/05/2010

Corresponding Author:

E. B. Anyanwu,

Department of Family Medicine, Faculty of Clinical Medicine, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

E-mail: ebirian@yayoo.com